

Oxidative Coupling of *o*- and *p*-Cresols with Alkaline Potassium Ferricyanide

P. L. MAJUMDER* and ANJALI KUNDU

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, Calcutta-700 009

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Oxidative coupling of *p*-cresol with alkaline $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ has been reinvestigated. This has yielded, besides the previously reported compounds (1), (2) and (3), two new products (4a) and (5). Detailed spectroscopic analyses of all the compounds including ^{13}C nmr studies of 1 and the tetraacetyl derivative of 4a have been made to confirm their structures. *o*-Cresol under identical reaction condition gave, in addition to a trace of an uncharacterised modified trimer, the tetramer (6). Its structure has also been settled by spectral evidence.

OXIDATIVE phenol coupling^{1,2} has been shown to be an obligatory process in the biosynthesis of a wide variety of natural products, viz., some isoquinoline alkaloids, the lignans and a number of dimeric polyphenolics. This has evoked considerable interest for extensive laboratory studies on this reaction with various phenolic substrates³. Besides model oxidation studies with simple phenols, biomimetic syntheses⁴ of a number of natural products and their close structural analogues have been made during the last few decades by oxidative coupling of appropriate phenolic precursors. As part of our programme of similar biomimetic synthesis of phenolic natural products, we have studied the oxidation of *o*-cresol with alkaline $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ and made a thorough reinvestigation of the same reaction with *p*-cresol with a view to ascertaining the steric and electronic factors which determine the mode of coupling and the relative yields of the various coupled products. The results of this investigation are presented here.

Results and Discussion

Oxidation of *p*-cresol with alkaline $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ was first studied by Pummerer *et al*^{5a} and later by Barton *et al*^{5c}. They reported the isolation of three compounds, A, B and C which were assigned the structures (1), (2) and (3), respectively, with very little spectroscopic evidence in support of their formulations. We have reinvestigated the reaction and are able to isolate, besides A, B and C, two new compounds, D and E. We have made detailed spectroscopic studies of all the compounds, which not only helped us to confirm the structures of the previously isolated compounds but also to establish the structures of the new compounds isolated by us.

Compound A, $C_{14}H_{14}O_2$ (M^+ 214), m.p. 123°, λ_{max} 223, 260 and 301 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.30, 3.27 and 3.50), also known as Pummerer's ketone, shows in its ir spectrum a band at 1665 cm^{-1} for a conjugated car-

bonyl function. The 1H nmr spectrum of the compound showing signals at δ 5.82 and 6.60 (each 1H,

d, $J=10$ Hz; $-\overset{|}{\underset{|}{C}}-C=CH-C=O$), 2.80 (2H, doublet of AB q, $J_1=16$ Hz, $J_2=3$ Hz; $-\overset{|}{O}-CH-CH_2$

$-\overset{|}{C}-$), 4.60 (1H, m; $-\overset{|}{O}-CH-CH_2-$), 2.24 (3H, s; Ar- CH_3), 1.49 [3H, s; Ar- $C(CH_3)-CH=CH$

$-\overset{|}{C}=O$], 6.35 (1H, dd, $J_1=10$ Hz and $J_2=2.5$ Hz; Ar- H), 6.86 (1H, d, $J=10$ Hz; Ar- H) and 6.90 (1H, q, $J=2.5$ Hz; Ar- H), strongly supports the structure (1) assigned to it. This was further confirmed by the ^{13}C nmr spectral data of the compound. The carbon chemical shifts of compound A (Table 1), which accounts for all the fourteen carbon atoms of the compound, were assigned on the basis of the splitting observed in its SFORD spectrum and by comparison with the δ_c values of structurally similar compounds⁵. The relatively downfield shifts of C-5a and C-9 have been attributed to the additional β -effects of the C-9a-methyl group, while the upfield shift of C-8 is at least partly due to the γ^+ -effect of the same methyl group.

The uv, ir and pmr spectral data of B, $C_{14}H_{14}O_2$, m.p. 153°, and C, $C_{21}H_{20}O_3$, m.p. 195° are also in conformity with structures (2) and (3), respectively, the *ortho-ortho* coupling in each case is supported by the splitting patterns of the aromatic protons in their pmr spectra.

Compound D, $C_{14}H_{14}O_3$, obtained as a pale yellow thick liquid shows in its ir spectrum a band for phenolic OH (ν_{max} 3500 cm^{-1}). The presence of only one such group in D was indicated by a one-proton singlet at δ 5.38 (disappeared on deuterium exchange) in the pmr spectrum of the compound,

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which in addition also shows signals for two aromatic methyls (δ 2.15 and 2.25) and seven aromatic protons. These data coupled with the splitting patterns of the aromatic protons in the pmr spectrum of **D** suggest structure (5) for the compound.

Compound **E** was isolated as its tetraacetate, $C_{36}H_{34}O_8$, m.p. 171°. The MS of the tetraacetyl derivative of **E** did not show the molecular ion, the highest peak being observed at m/z 552 ($M^+ - 42$). The latter is followed by peaks at m/z 510, 468 and 426 corresponding to sequential loss of three ketene units. The pmr spectrum of the tetraacetate shows signals for four acetoxy functions (δ 1.72 and 2.08, each 6H, s), four aromatic methyls (δ 2.36, 12H, s) and ten aromatic protons at δ 7.25-7.50. The uv, ir and the foregoing spectral data of the tetraacetate are in accord with the structure (4b). The parent phenol **E** should, therefore have the structure (4a). The *ortho-ortho* coupling of compound **E** (4a) was supported by the ^{13}C nmr spectral data of its tetraacetyl derivative (Table 1).

TABLE 1—CARBON CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF 1 AND 4b

1		4b	
Carbon atom	δ_{ppm} (multiplicity in SFORD)	Carbon atom	δ_{ppm} (multiplicity in SFORD)
C-1	125.7 (d)	C-1, C-1'''	130.0 (s)
C-2	132.2 (s) ^a	C-1', C-1''	130.9 (s)
		C-3', C-3''	
C-3	129.6 (d)	C-2, C-2'''	145.6 (s)
C-4	123.0 (d)	C-2', C-2''	143.5 (s)
C-4a	149.4 (s)	C-3, C-3'''	122.1 (d)
C-5a	86.5 (d)	C-4, C-4'''	129.2 (d) ^e
C-6	37.5 (t)	C-6, C-6'''	131.1 (d) ^c
C-7	194.8 (s)	C-6', C-6''	131.2 (d) ^e
C-8	110.0 (d)	C-4', C-4''	131.6 (d) ^e
C-9	149.4 (d)	C-5, C-5'''	135.1 (s) ^d
C-9a	45.0 (s)	C-5', C-5''	135.3 (s) ^d
C-9b	131.0 (s) ^a	MeCOO-	168.7 (s) ^f
		CH ₂ -CO-O	169.3 (s) ^f
C-9a-Me	20.8 (q) ^b	MeCOO-	20.0 (q) ^e
C-2-Me	21.4 (q) ^b	Me-Ar	20.7 (q) ^e

^a The values are in ppm downfield from TMS: $\delta(TMS) = \delta(CDCl_3) + 76.9$ ppm.

^{a-e} Values are interchangeable.

The coupling profile as revealed by the oxidation products of *p*- and *o*-cresol would thus serve as an useful guide for biomimetic synthesis of appropriate phenolic natural products.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in a Kofler block and are uncorrected. Silica gel (60-100 mesh) was used for column chromatography and silica gel G for tlc. UV spectra were measured in 95% aldehyde-free EtOH and ir spectra were run in KBr on a Beckman Infrared spectrophotometer (model 20). 1H and ^{13}C nmr spectra were recorded in a Varian CFT-20 instrument operating at 80 MHz and 20 MHz, respectively, using $CDCl_3$ as the solvent and TMS as the internal standard. Chemical shifts are expressed in δ_{ppm} . MS were run in a DS-55 instrument equipped with a direct inlet system and operating at 70 eV. All the analytical samples were routinely dried over P_2O_5 at 80° for 24 hr in *vacuo* and were tested for purity by tlc and mass spectrometry. Anhydrous Na_2SO_4 was used for drying organic solvents and petrol used had b.p. 30-80°.

Unlike *p*-cresol, *o*-cresol underwent extensive polymerisation under identical reaction condition and afforded compound **F**, $C_{28}H_{26}O_4$ ($M^+ 426$), m.p. 165°, and traces of an uncharacterised modified trimer **G**, $C_{21}H_{18}O_3$ ($M^+ 318$), m.p. 235°, as the only isolable products. Compound **F** shows uv absorption at λ_{max} 250 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.59) and exhibits a ir band at ν_{max} 3100 cm^{-1} for phenolic hydroxyl function. Presence of four such groups in **F** was also indicated by its pmr spectrum showing a four-proton singlet at δ 5.14 (disappeared on deuterium exchange). The spectrum in addition revealed signals for four aromatic methyls (δ 2.25 and 2.29, each 6H, s) and ten aromatic protons (δ 6.87-7.35). The splitting patterns of the aromatic proton signals when considered together with the above spectral data suggest structure (6) for compound **F**.

Oxidation of *p*-cresol with alkaline $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$: Anhydrous Na_2CO_3 (12.5 g) in water (165 ml) was taken in a three necked R.B. flask (1 litre) and the solution was deaerated with oxygen-free nitrogen. *p*-Cresol (1.5 g) was added to it and brought into solution by gentle warming. The solution was cooled to 0. $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ (6.5 g) in water (165 ml) was added slowly from a dropping funnel to the above solution during 30 min, keeping the solution under constant stirring. After a further 30 min stirring the solution was extracted with ether. The ether extract was extracted with 1 *N* NaOH soln. The resultant ether layer was dried and the solvent removed to give a semi-solid mass (frac. A). The aqueous alkaline solution was acidified with 6 *N* H_2SO_4 in the cold and extracted with ether, dried and the solvent removed to give a semi-solid residue (frac. B).

Frac. A was chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (20 : 1) eluate gave **1** (0.70 g), crystallised from petrol, m.p. 123°; λ_{max} (log ϵ): 223 (4.30), 260 (3.27) and 301 (3.50) nm; ν_{max} : 1665 cm^{-1} (conjugated $>C=O$); δ_{ppm} : 1.49 (3H, s; 9a-Me), 2.24 (3H, s; 2-Me), 4.60 (1H, m; H-5a), 2.80 (2H, doublet of ABq, $J_1=16$ Hz and $J_2=3$ Hz; H_a-6), 5.82 (1H, d, $J=10$ Hz; H-8), 6.35 (1H, dd, $J_1=10$ Hz, $J_2=2.5$ Hz; H-3), 6.60 (1H, d, $J=10$ Hz; H-9), 6.86 (1H, d, $J=10$ Hz; H-4) and 6.90 (1H, d, $J=2.5$ Hz; H-1).

Chromatography of frac. B gave in the petrol-EtOAc (80 : 1) eluate **5** (0.03 g) as a pale yellow thick liquid. (Found: C, 78.49; H, 6.50. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 78.50; H, 6.54%). λ_{max} : 212 and 278 nm; ν_{max} : 3500 cm^{-1} (OH); δ_{ppm} : 2.15 (3H, s; Ar-Me), 2.25 (3H, s; Ar-Me), 5.38 (1H, s, disappeared on deuteration; Ar-OH), 6.55 (1H, br. s; H-6), 6.68 (1H, d, $J=8$ Hz, H-3), 6.83 (1H, dd, $J_1=8$ Hz, $J_2=2.5$ Hz; H-4), 6.80 (2H, doublet with fine splitting, $J=8$ Hz; H-2', H-6') and 7.05 (2H, doublet with fine splitting, $J=8$ Hz; H-3', H-5').

Further elution of the column with petrol-EtOAc (50 : 1) gave unconverted *p*-cresol (0.30 g). The petrol-EtOAc eluate (20 : 1) afforded **2** (0.045 g), crystallised from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 153°; λ_{max} (log ϵ): 219 (4.29) and 292 (3.65) nm; ν_{max} : 3100 cm^{-1} (OH); δ : 2.25 (6H, s; Ar-Me), 5.75 (2H, s, disappeared on deuteration; Ar-OH), 6.83 (2H, dd, $J_1=10$ Hz, $J_2=2.5$ Hz; H-4, H-4'), 6.93 (2H, d, $J=10$ Hz; H-3, H-3'), 7.05 (2H, d, $J=2.5$ Hz; H-6, H-6'). The petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) eluate gave **3** (0.06 g), crystallised from petrol-benzene, m.p. 195°; λ_{max} (log ϵ): 246 (4.42), 292 (4.01) and 332 (4.0) nm; ν_{max} : 3400 cm^{-1} (OH); δ : 2.25 (6H, s; Ar-Me), 2.31 (3H, s; Ar-Me), 6.0 (3H, br. signal, disappeared on deuteration; Ar-OH), 6.75-7.10 (8H, m; Ar-H). The later fractions of petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) eluate and the early fractions of the petrol-EtOAc (5 : 1) eluate gave **4a** (0.085 g) containing traces of **3**, which could not be purified by crystallisation. The mixture was acetylated with Ac_2O/Py and the acetylated mixture was chromatographed. The early fractions of the petrol-EtOAc

(20 : 1) eluate gave triacetate of **3**, crystallised from petrol, m.p. 107°. The later fractions of the same eluate gave **4b** (0.075 g), crystallised from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 171°. (Found: C, 72.76; H, 5.65. $C_{28}H_{24}O_8$ requires C, 72.73; H, 5.72%). λ_{max} (log ϵ): 220 (4.71) nm; ν_{max} : 1220 and 1760 cm^{-1} (OAc); δ : 1.72 (6H, s; 2'- and 2''-OCOC H_3), 2.08 (6H, s; 2- and 2''-OCOC H_3), 2.36 (12H, s; Ar-Me), 7.25-7.50 (10H, m; Ar-H); m/z (relative abundance): 552 (28.8), 510 (47.2), 492 (7.9), 468 (64.8), 450 (10.4), 426 (100), 408 (17.0), 392 (5.2), 211 (7.7) and 43 (28.1) (it does not show the M^+).

Oxidation of *o*-cresol with alkaline $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$: Under identical reaction conditions a solution of *o*-cresol (4.5 g) in water (495 ml) containing Na_2CO_3 (37.5 g) was treated with $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ (19.5 g) in water (480 ml). The product was extracted with ether, washed with water, dried and chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (80 : 1) eluate gave **6** (0.005 g), crystallised from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 235°; ν_{max} : 1675 cm^{-1} (conjugated $>C=O$); δ_{ppm} : 1.80 (3H, s), 2.24 (6H, s), 4.82 (1H, m), 5.35 (1H, m), 6.78-7.85 (6H, m); m/z (relative abundance) 318 (M^+ , 100), 290 (14.1), 289 (55.2), 276 (19.7), 275 (74.5), 273 (17.2), 249 (15.8) and 53 (21.5). Further elution of the column with petrol-EtOAc (50 : 1) gave unconverted *o*-cresol (1 g). The petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) eluate gave **6** (0.04 g), crystallised from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 165°. (Found: C, 78.60; H, 6.15. $C_{28}H_{28}O_4$ requires C, 78.87; H, 6.10%). λ_{max} (log ϵ): 250 (4.59) nm; ν_{max} : 3100 cm^{-1} (OH); δ_{ppm} : 2.25 (6H, s; Ar-Me), 2.29 (6H, s; Ar-Me), 5.14 (4H, s, disappeared on deuteration exchange; Ar-OH), 6.87 (2H, d, $J=10$ Hz; H-5 and H-5''), 7.02 (2H, dd, $J_1=10$ Hz, $J_2=3$ Hz; H-6 and H-6''), 7.17 (4H, d, $J=3$ Hz; H-2, H-2', H-2'', H-4'), 7.35 (2H, d, $J=3$ Hz; H-6', H-6''); m/z (relative abundance): 426 (M^+ , 100), 320 (65.5), 213 (8.9), 149 (34.7), 97 (20.2), 83 (97), 69 (28.1), 57 (54) and 43 (42.4).

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